

An Approximate Procedure for Calculating the Ultimate Load of columns in Sway Steel Frames with Semi-Rigid Connections

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ABSTRACT

Calculating the ultimate load of a column in a sway framed structure involves in the currently used design method, the calculation of the column effective length and utilizing the interaction formulas or tables. Therefore, no allowance is usually made for the effects of the presence of semi rigid connections or the presence of infill panels.

In this paper a new and simple design procedure is recommend to calculate the ultimate load of a framed column allowing for the presence of rotational end restraints, semi rigid connections, the column end moments resulted from the applied vertical and horizontal loading and infill panels in real steel structure.

In order to verify the accuracy of the recommended method to predict good and safe estimations of framed column ultimate loads several examples have been solved utilizing the recommended procedure and the results were compared to those obtained using a second order computer program and good correlation had been obtained. Therefore, the accuracy of the proposed method to predict the behaviour of practical steel columns in framed structures has been verified.

Keywords: Column Ultimate Loads, Semi Rigid Connections, Infill Panels, Steel Structure.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the design of framed columns, two classes of steel structures are recognized as found in (1) and these are:

- 'Simple construction' where the columns are usually designed as axially loaded elements with nominal moments transferred from beams to columns to account for the eccentricities between the center line of the column and the assumed center of bearing at the connection.
- 'Continuous construction' in which a similar procedure for design columns in 'simple construction' is normally used, except that the bending moments transmitted to the column ends are defined by a frame analysis (linear or nonlinear analysis as appropriate).

The former class is almost inevitably non-sway structures since the rotational discontinuity between the columns and the beams requires the existence of a bracing system to resist lateral loading while the second is sway structures since lateral loading is resisted by the framed elements, i.e. the beams and the columns. Calculating the ultimate load of a framed column in sway structures involves, in the currently used design method, the calculation of the column effective length and utilizing the interaction formulae or tables.

In this paper, a simple model has been adopted to calculate the ultimate loads of framed columns in sway structures without the need to calculate neither the maximum bending moments of the column nor the effective length factor.

2. THE PROPOSED MODEL

A previous study conducted by (2,4) has shown that the behavior of framed columns in sway structures is influenced by:

- The rotational end restraints provided at the column ends,
- The ratio of horizontal to the vertical loads applied to the column and
- Initial imperfection of the column
- The presence of infill panels

Therefore, the simple model shown in *Fig. 1* has been used which consists of a sway column supported by two beams at each end and subjected at its tip to horizontal and vertical loads.

Fig 1. The simple model used in the proposed analysis

In this study the presence of infill panels is simulated by an elastic spring connected to the top right beam with a constant elastic stiffness S . This model has been chosen because it allows for the main influence factors mentioned above. Calculating end moments of the model assuming positive anti-clock wise gives:

- Joint 1:

$$M_{12} = \frac{EI_c}{L_c} \left[s\theta_1 + sc\theta_2 + \frac{s(1+c)}{L_c} \delta \right] \quad (1)$$

For beam 1A and 1B: using the equation of member with Semi-rigid joints

$$M_{1A} = M_{1B} = \frac{EI_{bl}}{L_b} \left[3 \left(\frac{1}{1+3\beta_1} \right) \theta_1 \right]$$

Where $P_E = \frac{\pi^2 EI_c}{L_c^2}$; $\rho = \frac{P}{P_E}$; $\alpha = \frac{\pi\sqrt{\rho}}{2}$; $s = \frac{\alpha(1-2\alpha \cot g(2\alpha))}{\tan(\alpha) - \alpha}$; $c = \frac{2\alpha - \sin(2\alpha)}{\sin(2\alpha) - 2\alpha \cos(2\alpha)}$; $\beta_1 = \frac{EI_{bl}}{L_b R_1}$ (2)

Equilibrium at joint 1 requires that:

$$\sum_i M = 0 \rightarrow M_{12} + M_{1B} + M_{1A} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\left[\frac{EI_c}{L_c} s + \frac{2EI_{bl}}{L_b} \left(\frac{3}{1+3\beta_1} \right) \right] \theta_1 + \frac{EI_c}{L_c} cs\theta_2 + \frac{EI_c}{L_c} \frac{s(1+c)}{L_c} \delta = 0 \quad (4)$$

- Joint 2:

$$M_{21} = \frac{EI_c}{L_c} \left[s\theta_2 + sc\theta_1 + \frac{s(1+c)}{L_c} \delta \right] \quad (5)$$

$$M_{2C} = M_{2D} = \frac{EI_{bu}}{L_b} \left[3 \left(\frac{1}{1+3\beta_2} \right) \theta_2 \right] \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_2 M = 0 \rightarrow M_{21} + M_{2C} + M_{2D} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{EI_c}{L_c} cs\theta_1 + \left[\frac{EI_c}{L_c} s + \frac{2EI_{bu}}{L_b} \left(\frac{3}{1+3\beta_2} \right) \right] \theta_2 + \frac{EI_c}{L_c} \frac{s(1+c)}{L_c} \delta = 0 \quad (8)$$

Considering the equilibrium of the column:

$$\sum_{column} M = 0 \rightarrow M_{12} + M_{21} - P(\delta + \delta_0) - HL_c + (S\delta)L_c = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{EI_c}{L_c}(s + sc)\theta_1 + \frac{EI_c}{L_c}(s + sc)\theta_2 + \left(\frac{2EI_c}{L_c} \frac{s(1+c)}{L_c} - P + SL_c \right) \delta - P\delta_0 - HL_c = 0 \quad (10)$$

Where:

E: modulus of elasticity

δ_0 : column initial deflection

L_c : column Height

δ : column sway

L_b : upper and lower beam span

P: column vertical load

I_{bu} : upper beams moment of inertia

H: column horizontal load

I_{bl} : lower beams moment of inertia

R: connection rotational stiffness

θ_2, θ_1 : rotation at upper and lower ends.

s, c : stability functions

S: Elastic spring stiffness allows for the present of infill panels

By solving Eqs (4), (8) and (10), the values of θ_1, θ_2 and δ will be obtained. Substituting these values in Eq. (1) and with series of calculations, the column maximum end moment is:

$$M_{max} = M_{12} = PL_c \left(\frac{H}{P} + \frac{\delta_0}{L_c} \right) C \quad (11)$$

$$C = \frac{s[(A+c) + B(1+c)]}{s(1+c)(1+A+2B) - \rho\pi^2 B + K_3 B}, \quad B = \frac{-1}{s(1+c)} \left[\frac{6}{G_2} + s(1+cA) \right], \quad A = \frac{\frac{6}{G_2} + s(1-c)}{\frac{6}{G_1} + s(1-c)}$$

Where:

$$G_1 = \frac{\frac{6EI_c}{L_c}}{2 \left(\frac{3EI_{bl}}{L_b} \right) \left(\frac{1}{1+3\beta_1} \right)}, \quad G_2 = \frac{\frac{6EI_c}{L_c}}{2 \left(\frac{3EI_{bu}}{L_b} \right) \left(\frac{1}{1+3\beta_2} \right)}, \quad K_3 = \frac{SL_c^3}{EI_c}$$

G_1, G_2 the modified relative column to beam stiffness which takes into account semi-rigid joint effects. It should be noted that a conservative estimate of K_3 for practical frames is given in BS5950.

Calculating the column compression stress at end 1 gives:

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{P}{A_c} + \frac{M_{12}}{I_c} Y_{max} \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{P}{A_c} \left[1 + \frac{L_c \left(\frac{H}{P} + \frac{\delta_0}{L_c} \right) Ch}{2r^2} \right] \quad (13)$$

Equating the column maximum stress σ_{max} to the material yield stress of column σ_y (i.e.

$\sigma_{max} = \sigma_y$) and rearranging gives:

$$\frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_y} = \frac{P_{ult}}{P_y} = \frac{1}{1 + \left[\left(\frac{H}{P} + \frac{\delta_0}{L_c} \right) ChL_c \right] / 2r^2} \quad (14)$$

Where:

P_{ult} : column ultimate load

A_c : column section area

P_y : yielding load of the column

H/P: ratio of horizontal to vertical loads

σ_{ult} : column ultimate compressive stress
 σ_y : yield stress of material
h: height of the column section.

r: column radius of gyration
 δ_0/L_c : initial deflection to column height.

3. THE PROPOSED METHOD

In order to calculate the ultimate load of a column in a sway frame, Eq. (14) has to be calculated. This requires a trial and error procedure, i.e. a column ultimate load is assumed to calculate a refined value and this procedure is repeated until the differences between the assumed and the calculated value is arbitrary small. This procedure can be best achieved by writing an excel page.

As an alternative, a research, using the computer, has been performed by the author to produce a simple formula, as a simple alternative to Eq. 14, which can be used effectively in the design of sway columns, accepting that the column has equal rotational end restraints, i.e. $G_1 = G_2 = G$.

Most practical steel columns in sway frame, especially intermediate columns, approximately satisfy this assumption and if not the smallest end restraint of the column should be used conservatively with the proposed method. However, the ground floor columns normally have different rotational end restraints, i.e. either fully fixed or pinned at lower ends and partially restraint at upper ends, for the first case the column smallest rotational end restraint can be used with the proposed method. Although the second case is rare in practical frames since sway frames usually provided with almost fixed lower end to increase their stiffness against horizontal deflections, a special treatment for this type of columns is included.

3.1 Formula for Estimating Column Ultimate Loads

The behavior of framed columns in sway structures is influenced by the rotational end restraints provided at the column ends, the ratio of horizontal to the vertical loads applied to the column and initial imperfection of the column. Extensive computerized research has been achieved by the author to estimate the column ultimate loads in sway structures, has yielded the following formula:

$$\frac{P_{ult}}{P_y} \left(\frac{L_c}{r} \right)^{1.3} = 15 \times \left(\frac{H}{P} + \frac{\delta_0}{L_c} \right)^{-0.40} \times G^{-0.2} \quad \text{but} \quad \frac{25}{L_c} \leq G \leq \frac{750}{L_c} \quad (15)$$

Where G is the rotational end restraint

Two restrictions were imposed on the value of G in eq. (15)

- The first is $\frac{25}{L_c} \leq G$ since $\frac{25}{L_c} \leq G$ defines approximately the fixed restraint and any value of G smaller than $\frac{25}{L_c} \leq G$ does not seem practical to increase the ultimate load of the column.
- While the second is $G \leq \frac{750}{L_c}$ since $G \leq \frac{750}{L_c}$ presents hinged ends of the column and therefore its ultimate load approaches a value of zero.

These restrictions have been obtained from a huge parametric study conducted by the author and could not be presented in this paper. It should be noted here that, the proposed method (i.e. Eq. 15) has been obtained by curve fitting the parametric study obtained from Eq. (14), Therefore the proposed method includes both effect of geometric and material nonlinearity and only local buckling of column sections is not considered in this paper since such effect is usually included by respecting certain limitation on the ratio of width to thickness of the section plates.

3.2 A Hinged Column at End and Partially Restraint at Second End

Since Eq. (15) is developed for columns with equivalent upper and lower end restraints, appropriate modifications should be recommended before utilizing it for a column with a hinged end.

A formula to calculate the effective end restraints G' for this type of columns has been achieved by the author. The equivalent column sub-assembly is assumed to have equal upper and lower end restraints G' with same ultimate load as the real column sub-assembly, i.e. with one end pinned and

the other has G end restraints. Therefore, the problem of calculating the ultimate load of a column pinned at one end and provided with G restraints at the other is transferred to the problem of calculating the ultimate load of the equivalent column sub-assembly assuming that it is provided with imaginary upper and lower end restraints equal to G' (see Fig. 3).

G' is given in term of $\left(\frac{H}{P} + \frac{\delta_0}{L_c}\right)$ & G through the following equation:

$$G' = \frac{7 \times G^{0.2}}{1 - 7.5 \left(\frac{H}{P} + \frac{\delta_0}{L_c}\right)} \quad (16)$$

Fig 2. Actual and equivalent models used in the proposed method

3.3 The Influence of Partial Sway Bracing

In real structures the existence of infill panels will inevitably increase the resistance of these frames against lateral drift leading to an improvement in the structural performances. A simple and an attractive way to include such effect in practical multi-storey frames is presented elsewhere (3) by enhancing the ultimate load of framed columns obtained from neglecting the presence of infill panel by the factor $(1 + 0.1K_3)$ which modifies Eq. 15 to become:

$$\frac{P_{ult}}{P_y} \left(\frac{L_c}{r}\right)^{1.3} = (1 + 0.1K_3) \left(15 \times \left(\frac{H}{P} + \frac{\delta_0}{L_c}\right)^{-0.40} \times G^{-0.2}\right) \quad (17)$$

4. THE VERIFICATION OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

4.1 Column with Equal End Restraints

4.1.1 Example 1

In order to verify the accuracy of the proposed method to estimate the ultimate loads in sway structures, a structural program Robot (2020) using P-Delta analysis has been used to calculate the column ultimate loads of the sub-assembly shown in Fig. 1 with the following properties:

Beam section: UB 203x133x30, Column section: UC 152x152x23; $L_b = 300$ cm, $A_c = 29.2$ cm², $I_{bu} = I_{bl} = I_b = 2896$ cm⁴, $I_c = 1250$ cm⁴, $\sigma_y = 275$ N/mm²; $E = 210000$ N/mm²; $S=0$ no infill panel and $\left(\frac{H}{P} + \frac{\delta_0}{L_c}\right)_{=1\%}$. Typical extended end plate connection with rotational stiffness $R = 10000$ kN.m/rad.

is utilized. Several values of column heights ranged from (3.0-12.0 m) have been considered and the result is tabulated in Table 1.

Calculating the ultimate load of the column with height equal to 3.0 m in the proposed method involves the following: $L_c = 300$ cm; $r = \sqrt{1250/29.2} = 6.54$ cm; $L_c/r = 45.85$; $P_y = 29.2 \times 27.5 = 803$ kN

Calculating the column end restraints G: $G = \frac{(6EI_c/L_c)}{2(3EI_b/L_b)(\frac{1}{1+3\beta})}$ where $(\frac{1}{1+3\beta})$ is the modification factor

of G for frames with semi-rigid connections.

$$\beta = \frac{EI_b}{L_b R} = 0.20272, \frac{1}{1+3 \times 0.20272} = 0.621, G = \frac{1250/300}{0.621 \times (2896/300)} = 0.695$$

but $G \geq 0.545$ and $G \leq 16.35$ $G=0.695$

N.B. since upper and lower beams are all pinned at far ends and partially restrained at near ends hence each beam provides the column with rotational end restraint equal to $3EI_b/L_b$. For different beam end conditions see (3). Substituting into Eq. (15) gives: $\frac{P_{ult}}{P_y} \left(\frac{300}{6.54} \right)^{1.3} = 15 \times (0.01)^{-0.4} \times 0.695^{-0.2}$

and solving gives $P_{ult} = 565\text{kN}$.

Similar calculation carried out for the rest of column heights and the result tabulated in Table 1 column 3. Utilizing Eq. 14 to calculate an approximation to the column ultimate load provides column 4. Employing computer program ROBOT (2020) using P-Delta analysis to calculate the column ultimate loads provides column 5 in Table 1, where it can be seen that, results obtained from the proposed methods (Eq.14 and Eq.15) are well compared to those obtained from ROBOT (2020).

Table 1. Ultimate load of the column in example 1

Column height (cm)	L_c/r	Prop. Method Eq.15 (kN)	Prop Method Eq.14 (kN)	ROBOT 2020 (kN)
300	45.85	565	585	580
400	61.14	412	503	490
600	91.7	264	353	340
800	122.27	192	245	230
1000	152.84	151	176	163
1200	183.41	123	131	120

4.1.2 Example 2

Calculating the column ultimate loads of the sub-assembly shown in Fig. 1 with beam span $L_b = 1200$ cm and $(H/P + \delta_0/L_c) = 10\%$ is shown in Table 2 with same process used in Table 1

Beam section: UB 203x133x30, Column section: UC 152x152x23 $L_b = 1200$ cm, $A_c = 29.2$ cm², $I_{bu} = I_{bl} = I_b = 2896$ cm⁴, $I_c = 1250$ cm⁴, $\sigma_y = 275$ N/mm²; $E = 210000$ N/mm²; $S=0$ no infill panel. Typical extended end plate connection with rotational stiffness $R= 10000$ kN.m/rad.

Table 2. Ultimate load of the column in example 2

Column height (cm)	L_c/r	Prop. Method Eq.15 (kN)	Prop. Method Eq.14 (kN)	ROBOT 2020 (kN)
300	45.85	182	192	195
400	61.14	133	149	153
600	91.7	85	101	103
800	122.27	62	75	76
1000	152.84	48	58	59
1200	183.41	39	47	48

Once again the proposed methods provide a reasonably safe estimate of the column ultimate loads.

4.1.3 Example 3

Calculating the ultimate load of the column in Fig. 1 for different connection rotational stiffness with beam span $L_b=300$ cm and $(H/P + \delta_0/L_c) = 1\%$ is shown in Table 3 with same process used in Table 1
Beam section: UB 203x133x30, Column section: UC 152x152x23; $A_c = 29.2$ cm², $I_{bu} = I_{bl} = I_b = 2896$

cm^4 , $I_c = 1250 \text{ cm}^4$, $\sigma_y = 275 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $E = 210000 \text{ N/mm}^2$. Typical flush end plate connection with rotational stiffness $R = 2900 \text{ kN.m/rad}$; $S = 0$ no infill panel.

Table 3. Ultimate load of the column in example 3

Column height (cm)	L_c/r	Prop. Method Eq.15 (kN)	Prop. Method Eq.14 (kN)	ROBOT 2020 (kN)
300	45.85	496	561	565
400	61.14	361	472	478
600	91.7	231	321	323
800	122.27	168	222	215
1000	152.84	132	161	155
1200	183.41	108	121	113

Close correlations were found between the proposed methods and ROBOT 2020.

4.1.4 A Hinged Column at One End

In order to demonstrate the ability of the proposed methods to handle columns hinged at one end the sub assemblage shown in *Fig.2* is employed with the following properties: $I_{bl} = 0.0$; $I_{bu} = 2896 \text{ cm}^4$; $L_b = 300 \text{ cm}$; $I_c = 1250 \text{ cm}^4$; $(H/P + \delta_0/L_c) = 5\%$; $S = 0$ no infill panel. The utilized joint is typical extended end plate connection with rotational stiffness $R = 10000 \text{ kN.m/rad}$. Several column heights equal to (400, 600, 800, 1000 and 1200) have been considered. These columns are assumed to be connected to perfect hinges at lower end and connected to two equal beams simply supported at the higher end. The resultant ultimate loads are tabulated in *Table4*.

Calculating the equivalent end restraints G' for the first case (column height $L_c = 400$) can be achieved by the following steps:

Calculating the actual end restraints G for the partially restraints end of the column (the lower end is assumed to be pinned) gives $G = \frac{1250/400}{0.623 \times (2896/300)} = 0.520$ (see column 2 of *Table 4*)

Calculating the equivalent effective column end restraints: $G' = \frac{7 \times 0.520^{0.2}}{1 - 7.5 \times 0.05} = 9.82$

Employing *Eq. (15)* to calculate an estimate of the ultimate column load noting that G should be substituted by G' gives $P_{ult} = 119 \text{ kN}$.

Utilizing same process for other column heights produced column 4 in *Table 4*.

Table 4. Ultimate column load of the sub-assemblage shown in Fig.2

Column height (cm)	G	G'	Prop. Method (kN) Eq.15	Prop. Method (kN) Eq.14	ROBOT 2020 (kN)
400	0.520	9.82	119	126	130
600	0.346	9.06	71	77	80
800	0.259	8.55	50	52	59
1000	0.208	8.18	38	37	-
1200	0.173	7.88	30	28	-

Using P-Delta analysis in ROBOT 2020 gives column 6 in *Table 4* where it can be seen that, a close correlations of column ultimate loads were found between the proposed methods and ROBOT 2020 except for column heights (1000 and 1200 cm) since structures become very flexible and accurate results could not be obtained from ROBOT 2020.

4.1.5 A Column with Infill Panels

In order to demonstrate that the proposed methods can handle columns with infill panels the sub assemblage shown in *Fig.1* is employed with the following properties:

$I_{bl} = 2896 \text{ cm}^4$; $I_{bu} = 2896 \text{ cm}^4$; $L_b = 300 \text{ cm}$; $I_c = 1250 \text{ cm}^4$; $(H/P + \delta_0/L_c) = 10\%$

The utilized joint is typical flush end plate connection with rotational stiffness $R= 2900 \text{ kN.m/rad}$. These columns are assumed to be connected to elastic spring stiffness S . Several relative infill panel stiffnesses $K3$ are considered (0, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10). It worth mentioning here that BS5950 restrict $K3$ not to exceed 2. The resultant ultimate loads are tabulated in Table 5. Employing Eq. (17) to calculate an estimate of the ultimate column load provides column 3 While Eq. (14) gives column 4.

Table 5. Ultimate column load of the sub-assembly shown in Fig.1 with infill panel

K3	S kN/cm	Prop. Method (kN) Eq. 17	Prop. Method (kN) Eq.14	ROBOT 2020 (kN)
0	0	197	197	205
2	1.944	237	252	260
4	3.89	276	300	310
6	5.83	316	340	350
8	7.78	355	374	386
10	9.72	395	404	415

Using P-Delta analysis in ROBOT 2020 gives column 5 in Table 5 where it can be seen that, a close and safe correlations of column ultimate loads were found between the proposed methods and ROBOT 2020 results.

It should be noted that, in the proposed methods, allowing for the influence of the column end moments is accomplished implicitly. Such moments resulted from:

- 1- The presence of lateral loads in sway structures,
- 2- The presence of rotational end restraints and
- 3- The presence of vertical loads applied to the beams.

Both items 1 and 2 are included in the proposed method and only item 3 has been ignored since, in the development of the proposed method, the column is assumed to be loaded by an axial vertical load with no loads on the beams. In practical frames however, three categories of columns exist which are:

- Columns located on the windward side of the frame in which the bending moments due to vertical loads are of opposite sign to those arising due to horizontal loads therefore the total column bending moments are likely to be reduced. The proposed method provides conservative estimations for the inelastic column ultimate loads.
- Interior columns where the bending moments due to the applied vertical loads are approximately balanced. The proposed method is ideally suited this category of column.
- Columns located on the leeward side of the frame with bending moments due to vertical loads are additive to those due to horizontal loads, therefore the proposed method is un-conservative here.

Nevertheless, the proposed method can still be used to design these columns since it is demonstrated to be conservative (see Tables 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) with satisfactory safety margins.

4.2 Employing The Proposed Method for First Selection of Framed Sections

To demonstrate that, the proposed method can be used effectively for making first selections of column sections of practical frames. Two examples shown in Fig. 3 are utilized where the frame loading and dimensions are arbitrarily chosen by the authors. In these examples the proposed method Eq. (15) is employed to obtain a first selection of framed column sections and the result is then checked by utilizing structural program ROBOT 2020 using P-Delta analysis.

4.2.1 Frame (a) in Figure (3)

A gross estimate of the maximum bending moment of the beam, taking it as simply supported over

$$M_{b,\max} = \frac{0.50 \times 400^2}{8 \times 100} = 100 \text{ kN.m}$$

the full beam span, is obtained:

It should be noted here that beam bending moments resulted from the presence of horizontal loads are not considered since the vertical loading is more critical for frame with few stories. Choose UB254×146×37 with beam bending moment capacity equal to $M_b=119 \text{ kN.m}$, hence beam stress ratio equal to $(sr = \frac{100}{119} = 0.84)$. For this frame we have $(P = \frac{0.50 \times 400}{2} = 100 \text{ kN}; H = 2 \text{ kN}; \delta_0 = 0)$

Fig 3. Frame (a) with extended end plate joints and Frame (b) with flush end plate joints

To take a section selection of the frame column and accepting in the first trial $G = 1; L/r \cong 100$ gives:

$$G \cong 1; L/r \cong 100 \xrightarrow{\text{Eq.16}} G' = 8.23 \xrightarrow{\text{Eq.15}}$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{ult}}{\sigma_y} \cong 0.12 \rightarrow \sigma_{ult} = 0.12 \times 27.5 = 3.25 \text{ kN/cm}^2$$

$$A_{req} = \frac{100}{3.25} = 30.76 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ choose UC152} \times 152 \times 30$$

$$\text{With } (r = 6.75 \text{ cm}; A = 38.3 \text{ cm}^2; I_x = 1748 \text{ cm}^4)$$

$$G \cong 0.074; L/r \cong 88.9 \xrightarrow{\text{Eq.16}} G' = 6.38 \xrightarrow{\text{Eq.15}}$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{ult}}{\sigma_y} \cong 0.144 \rightarrow \sigma_{ult} = 0.144 \times 27.5 = 2.56398 \text{ kN/cm}^2$$

$$A_{req} = \frac{100}{3.98} = 25.12 \text{ cm}^2 < 38.3 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ (ok)}$$

$$P_{ult} = 3.98 \times 38.3 = 152.4 \text{ kN} \quad \text{Stress ratio}$$

$$(sr = \frac{100}{152.4} = 0.66).$$

Same selection has been used for columns located on windward and leeward sides of the frame despite the fact that the moment resulted from the horizontal loading are additive to that resulted from the vertical loading for column located on the leeward side of the frame.

Utilizing ROBOT 2020 with the selected cross sections of the elements provides column 5 in Table 6 where it can be noticed that the primary selection of section is appropriate.

Table 6. Comparison of proposed method and ROBOT 2020 for a first selection of frame sections

			Stress ratio (proposed method)	Stress ratio ROBOT
Frame a	Beam section	UB 254x146x37	0.84	0.65
	Column section	UC 152x152x30	0.66	0.73 (leeward side)
Frame b	Beam upper section	UB 203x130x30	0.99	0.72
	Beam lower section	UB 254x146x31	0.95	0.68
	Column section	upper UC 152x152x23	0.57	0.67(leeward side)
	Column section	lower UC 152x152x30	1.06	0.67(leeward side)

4.2.2 Frame (b) in Figure (4)

Utilizing same procedure as for frame (a) and noting that G is calculated for all frame columns instead of G' (there is no hinged end) gives:

- **Section for upper beam:**

$UB203 \times 130 \times 30$ ($M_{\max} = 76.6 \text{ kN.m}$; $M_b = 77 \text{ kN.m}$ with stress ratio $sr = 76.6/77 = 0.99$)

- **Section for lower beam:**

$UB254 \times 146 \times 31$ ($M_{\max} = 91.9 \text{ kN.m}$; $M_b = 96.5 \text{ kN.m}$ with stress ratio $sr = 91.9/96.5 = 0.95$)

-**Section for second storey columns:**

Accepting in the first trial $G = 1$; $L/r \cong 100$ and $(H/P)=0.085$ gives:

$$\frac{\sigma_{ult}}{\sigma_y} \cong 0.101 \rightarrow \sigma_{ult} = 0.101 \times 27.5 = 2.78 \text{ kN/cm}^2 \quad A_{req} = 16.8 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$A_{req} = \frac{87.5}{2.78} = 31.5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ choose UC152} \times 152 \times 23 \quad A_{available} = 29.8 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$\beta \cong 0.6; G = 1.05, L/r \cong 61.6 \xrightarrow{\text{Eq.15}} \sigma_{ult} = 5.21 \text{ kN/cm}^2; (sr = \frac{16.8}{29.2} = 0.57).$$

-**Section for first storey columns:**

Accepting for the first trial $\sigma_{ult} = 5.21 \text{ kN/cm}^2$ which is taken from last trial of top story column

$$\sigma_{ult} = 5.21 \text{ kN/cm}^2 \rightarrow A_{required} = \frac{192.5}{5.21} = 36.9 \text{ cm}^2$$

ultimate stress

Choose (UC 152×152×30) ($A_{available} = 38.3 \text{ cm}^2$) $\beta \cong 0.6; G = 1.93, L/r \cong 59.2 \xrightarrow{\text{Eq.15}}$

$$\sigma_{ult} = 4.70 \text{ kN/cm}^2 \rightarrow A_{required} = \frac{192.5}{4.70} = 40.95 \text{ cm}^2 \quad (sr = \frac{40.93}{38.3} = 1.06).$$

These values are tabulated in rows 4-7 in Table 6 with those obtained from ROBOT. Table 6 shows once again that utilizing the proposed method for making primary selection of practical sway frame section provides suitable results for design offices.

5. CONCLUSION

The design of framed columns in sway structures normally accomplished by adopting a trial selection of the column section and then determining the column axial load and the bending moment pattern before employing interaction formulae to check the capacity and the overall stability of the column. This, of course, involves the calculation of the column effective length factor taking into account the inelastic behavior of the column.

In the proposed methods all these steps are incorporated simultaneously and only the end restraints of the considered column, the effect of semi-rigid joints and the ratio of the applied horizontal to vertical loads plus the ratio of the column upper initial deflection to the column height are required to obtain a safe estimate for the column's ultimate load. The proposed methods have been proven to be effective when used to make reasonable selections for column sections of practical frames and these selections can then be checked against interaction formulae available in most steel codes for designing beam-column elements.

6. REFERENCES

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